

SUBHASH CHANDRA BOSE AND HIS CONTRIBUTION IN INDIAN FREEDOM MOVEMENT

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Abstract

Subhash Chandra Bose, commonly known as 'Neta Ji' commands a respectable place in the annals of freedom movement of India. He had distinguished qualities of unparalleled courage, single minded devotion and patriotism. His only aim in life was to get Mother India out of British Slavery. For this, he not only sacrificed ICS but also his life. He was daring enough to move out of India, particularly when he was put under house arrest. Abroad he mobilized people, built an army, INA and waged war against the most powerful British Empire. The International circumstances during the last phase of second World War proved unfavourable and he, himself died in plane crash under mysterious circumstances. But his words and deeds still inspire the youth of India to do anything for the nation.

Key words: *Azad-Free; Hind-India; Fauz-Army; Banglar-Bengal; Khadi-Cotton; Sanyasi-who hs renounced the world*

Subhash Chandra Bose was born on 23rd January, 1897 in the family of renowned advocate Rao Bahadur Janaki Das Bose (who was member of Bengal legislative Council in 1912)¹ and Prabhati at Cuttack (now a days in Orissa). At that time Bengal, Bihar and Orissa were part of Bengal Presidency. In the joint family, he was among ninth child of his parents, sixth among the eight brothers. He was called 'Raja' by his Dai (Mid wife).² At the age of five years, he was admitted to Baptist Mission School which was having more female teachers than male. Most of them were natives of England. Environment in the school was

¹ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, Sterling Publishers Private Limited, New Delhi, 1988, pp.2

² Vinod Tiwari, Neta Ji Subhash Chandra Bose, White Publications (Hindi), Delhi, 2014, pp. 10

western and far away from the vernacular language and culture. Subhash could not get himself escaped from its impact. In 1909, at the age of 12 years he was admitted to Ravenshaw Collegiate School which was laying emphasis on Indian Culture. Here nationalist Principal Beni Madhav Das inculcated in Subhash the qualities of selflessness and sacrifice for motherland. Here students used to wear Indian dress i.e. Dhoti and Kurta. They were speaking vernacular language Bangla and learning Indian culture. Though it is very difficult for anyone to get himself adjusted in entirely new atmosphere but Subhash not only accustomed himself to this new environment but felt pride in Indian dresses and culture.³ He shared this change to his father also.

During his student life, he developed a strong love and affection not only for his motherland but also inclined towards mystic life. He wrote, “It was a period of acute mental conflict, causing untold suffering and agony, which could not be shared by any friends.”⁴ It was at this age of 15 years he had a chance to get literature of Swami Vivekananda. He started reading Swami Vivekananda and visiting Ramakrishna mission. Ideas of Swami Vivekananda influenced him a lot and shaped his character. He started practicing Yoga, doing meditation and living in such a peace that his friends started calling him ‘Sanyasi’. On one side was his love for nation and on the other he wished to go deeper inside. That is why, on the eve of first death anniversary of Khudi Ram Bose, a great revolutionary, he encouraged his fellow students to observe ‘Fast’ on August 11, 1910. Principal of the college too observed fast, and was punished by being transferred from Cuttack to Bengal. When Chechak spread in the nearby villages, he along with other students left no stone unturned to serve the villagers because he was pained to see the miseries of the people.

In 1913, he passed matriculation with second rank in Calcutta University. For higher studies, he was admitted to Presidency College, Calcutta. In Calcutta, he had an opportunity to listen and talk to great people like Rabindra Nath Tagore, Surindera Nath Bannerjee etc. He liked the combination of politics and spiritualism in Aurobindo. He passed intermediate but got average marks. This dissatisfactory result changed his mindset. Getting inspired from the intellect of Swami Vivekananda he devoted himself to studies. He was doing graduation

³ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, Samriti Sahitya (Hindi), Delhi, 2014, pp.11

⁴ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.9

in B. A. with philosophy.⁵ During this course an incident changed his view towards life. He was studying in library, a fellow student came to him and told that as usual Prof. E. F. Oaten of History is beating the students in the class.⁶ Mr. Oaten used to hate Indians and left no opportunity in humiliating them. Subhash Bose as Class representative, along with other students went to Principal James. However, the Principal in stead of listening to their grievances, told them to tender an apology to Mr. Oaten. It was indigestible to Subhash and his friends. They planned to teach a lesson to school officials by declaring strike in the school. It was for the first time in the history of India that strike was observed in any school against the teachers. They got the sympathy of Indian teachers. It continued for three days. Ultimately Mr. Oaten tendered apology but not to forget it. On another day, he slapped deliberately Subhash on his back for not walking properly. Subhash and his friends retaliated by beating him outside the college. It resulted in Subhash's expulsion from the college.⁷ He was out of studies for one year during which he formed a 'Sewa Dal' to serve the people.

In 1917, Sir Ashutosh Mukherjee, Vice-Chancellor, Calcutta University helped him in getting admission at Scottish Church College, Calcutta in B. A. 3rd year. Here he had the opportunity of getting military training. His Battalion captain Mr. Grey was impressed with his military skills. Subhash Bose himself wrote, "This training gave me something which I needed, the feeling of strength and self-confidence grew still further."⁸ Incidentally Mr. Oaten came for an inspection. He had been promoted to Director General in Education Department. He recognized Subhash but was compelled to change his opinion when he came to know the excellent qualities of Subhash especially when recommended by Mr. Grey. Subhash was appointed non-commissioned officer.

His father wanted him to go abroad for higher studies. In 1919, he went to London and got admitted to Cambridge school. He passed ICS on 22nd September, 1920 and stood fourth. However, he resigned from ICS on April 22nd, 1921 and came back to India. On the way he had a chance to meet Rabindranath Tagore. After reaching Bombay, he met Mahatma Gandhi on July 16, 1921.⁹ Both talked for almost one hour. He agreed to view points of

⁵ Dr. Sudha Singh, Mahan Krantikari Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose (Hindi), Prateek Publications, Delhi, 2016, pp.13

⁶ Vinod Tiwari, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.13

⁷ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.13

⁸ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.15

⁹ Anjali Singh, Mahan Krantikari Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose (Hindi), Vidyashree Publishing House, Delhi, 2015, pp.15

Gandhi Ji to some extent but difference of opinion too existed. At the advice of Gandhi Ji, he met C. R. Das. Both had a consensus on most of the issues and became intimate friends. Subhash was appointed Principal of National College.

In 1921, Prince of Wales visited India, at a time when Non-Cooperation movement was going on. So, Prince was boycotted all over India. In Calcutta, Subhash Bose took the lead. Subhash was led the non-cooperation movement in Bengal so impressively that 'The Statesman' wrote, "Congress got an able person (S. C. Bose) and govt. lost a capable officer."¹⁰ On December 10, 1921, he was arrested along with C R Das. When Mahatma Gandhi suspended non cooperation movement after the 'Chauri Chaura' violence, Subhash Bose in anguish commented "to sound the order of retreat just when the public enthusiasm was reaching the boiling point was nothing short of a national calamity."¹¹ Political movement stopped altogether. Bengal witnessed several floods in the last quarter of 1922, Subhash contributed along with young men of Bengal in providing relief to them. He was the head of the first group doing the relief work. Governor Litton too praised him for his splendid work.

When Swarajist party was formed by C. R. Das. Subhash too became its member and was appointed editor of the 'Banglar Katha', a journal started by C. R. Das. He was also in charge of organization and propaganda. When Swarajist Party won municipal corporation elections, Subhash was appointed as Chief Executive Officer. In this capacity, he revolutionized the system of cleanliness and administration. 'Volunteer corps was formed to sell 'Khadi'. This movement was so popular that Govt. had to ban it. Subhash decided to disobey and started sending volunteers in group of five. Their message was:

*"Khadi Pehno aur Pehnao
Swadeshi Vastuon ka Prayog Karo
Videshi maal ka Bahishkar karo"*¹²

He even criticized the British govt. when Gopinath Saha was hanged for shooting dead an English officer Mr. Dey. A resolution was passed in the state meeting of Bengal congress. Due to these activities, Govt. was all out to arrest him on one pretext or the other. Ultimately, he was arrested on 25th October, 1924 on the charges of supporting Bengal

¹⁰ Vinod Tiwari, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.24-25

¹¹ S. C. Bose, The Indian Struggle, 1920-42, Compiled by Netaji Research Bureau, Calcutta, Asia Publishing House, 1964, pp.73

¹² C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.28

revolutionaries. Bengal people built a lot of pressure to release Bose. Govt. had to allow him to look after the work of municipal corporation from Presidency jail. Later on, he was transferred to Berhampore jail and then to Mandley jail in Burma on 25th January, 1925.

Subhash contested Bengal State Legislative Assembly elections from Jail in November 1926 and won. Even then he was not released. He suffered Broncho pneumonia and 'medical examination disclosed that he was ill due to T. B.¹³ So, the doctors advised his release but govt. was adamant. In the meantime, New Superintendent of Jails Mr. Pindley joined. He strongly recommended his case and got him transferred to Almora Jail. On the way, he received the orders of his release after imprisonment of 2 years, 6 months and 21 days.

During these two and half years, political scenario had changed. C. R. Das was no more. Impact of Swarajist party had declined. Revolutionaries were taking prominent place under HSRA. At this juncture, British Govt sent Simon Commission to india. Congress decided to boycott Simon Commission as it was all white commission having no Indian part of it. Demonstrations were held at many places.

Subhash Bose along with Shoiab Queshi and Jawaharlal Nehru got elected General Secretary of the congress. But soon differences between Gandhi and subhash erupted and became prominent. On one side Gandhi did not like the military training of the volunteers as proposed by Bose, on the other hand, Bose was not happy over the Gandhi's response towards the revolutionaries. In fact, Subhash was combining the spirit of socialism and fascism. The very basics of socialism, which symbolize, justice, equality and love, were at the core of his approach towards people. He always relished the discipline and work efficiency of fascism and inculcated that in his organizational work. Youth were rallying behind Bose. After the economic depression of 1929, labourers were facing a lot of difficulties and they also supported Bose. He formed 'Congress Democratic Party' on January 2, 1930. Left leaning people joined it. He was again arrested in January 1930 on the charges of sedition for leading a march on the occasion of 'All Bengal Political Sufferers' Day'. After his release in September 1930, he toured the country, addressed meetings and organized people. He was elected president of 'Naujwan Bharat Sabha' in 1931.¹⁴

¹³ The Luminous Life of Subhash Chandra Bose, Edited Shyam Dua, Printline Books, Delhi, 2004, pp.27

¹⁴ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.61
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On January 1, 1932 Civil Disobedience Movement was launched by Congress and Bose was arrested on 2nd January while Gandhi ji and Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel were arrested on 4th January. After release, in February 1933, Bose went to Europe and toured many countries till 1936. He visited Europe again in 1937 till early 1938. He had a warm welcome at Venice. In Switzerland he met Vithalbhai Patel, elder brother of Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel. Vithalbhai Patel was former President of Indian Legislative Assembly. Both were having many things in common in ideology and approach towards means of Indian Freedom Movement. Both Subhash and Vithalbhai issued joint statement that also after suspension of the Civil Disobedience Movement by Mahatma Gandhi. Subhash remarked, "This newest work of suspending the Civil Disobedience Movement by Mr. Gandhi is the acceptance of his failure. It is our clear view that Gandhi has been unsuccessful as political leader. Time has come that congress should be reformatively reorganized on new principles and new methodology. It needs a new leader. It will be injustice to have hope from new programmes due to lack of coordination with old principles of Gandhi Ji. If congress itself could do such precious change, it will be the best, otherwise a new party from congress will have to be formed which will be founded on the reformative factors."¹⁵

His tour to Europe made him to understand the functioning of capitalism in many countries on one hand and socialism in Russia under Stalin on the other hand. He closely watched the working of Kamal Pasha, Mussolini, Hitler etc. He was of the firm opinion that one should be practical. Idealism alone without realism is of no use rather harmful for any society or nation. He was synthesizing the philosophy of swami Vivekananda and practical approach of Rabindra Nath Tagore in his concept of education. In a letter to the Secretary of Philosophical Society, Scottish Church College on September 9 1934 Subhash wrote that "Originality of thought is a priceless asset for every human being..... Subhash was of the decided view that manual training rather than memorization of text was necessary at the primary stage. This alone would make education, a thing of joy rather than fear and inculcate in them, the power of originality. We may logically say that Subhash would have found the modern mercenary tutorial homes, totally repugnant, since the atrophy all creative talents of the students and turn them, to use the words of poet Long-fellow, into dumb driven cattle."¹⁶ 'He met Romain Rolland, noble laureate, a staunch supporter of Gandhi's non-violent

¹⁵ Vinod Tiwari, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.44

¹⁶ The Luminous Life of Subhash Chandra Bose, Edited Shyam Dua, pp.60-61

movement. He met Benito Mussolini in December 1933 and conveyed him that he believed in revolution rather than reforms. Mussolini smilingly assured Indian freedom.’¹⁷

Subhash Bose got published his work ‘The Indian Struggle’ in 1934. Though it was banned in India but in London its reviews were published. His secretary Ms Emily Schenkel contributed a lot in this work. He returned India for a short period to attend the funeral of his father in December 1934. In 1936, he met J. L. Nehru at Switzerland who had gone there for the treatment of his wife. Kamla Nehru died on 24th February, 1936. When he came back in 1936, he was arrested at Bombay. J. L. Nehru criticized the British govt. for this and he made Subhash again member of the congress. On May 10, 1936 ‘All India Strike’ was observed for his release. As a result, he was put under House arrest in his brother’s house. His health deteriorated in December 1936 but was released on 17th march, 1937. On health grounds, he visited Europe again and this time, he married his beloved Ms Emily.

On January 8, 1938 he was in London when he got information that he had been elected president of the congress in his absence. So, he came back to Calcutta. Preparations for Haripura Session of the Congress were going on. On this 51st session of the congress, 51 gates were put with 51 national flags and Subhash’s chariot was pulled to hall by 51 bullocks. It was Subhash’s political coronation.¹⁸ In his presidential address said, “We people who have become the slaves of the British empire and are fighting for our as well other countries and are luckily fighting for economic liberation of British people.”¹⁹ He also raised the issue of labour unions and farmers. He was of the opinion that Congress should align these people. As Congress is the largest institution, people should be united under her. In this session, while delivering his longest speech, he raised every issue related to politics, economy and society. He vehemently attacked the divide and rule policy of the British and in the last, wishing long life for Gandhi Ji, stressed for the need of Gandhi Ji not only for India but also the solutions of the world problems. However, soon differences between them again emerged. He defeated the official candidate of Gandhi Ji, Pattabhai Sitaramaiya in 1939 for the post of president of the Congress. Gandhi Ji accepted the defeat as his own. Still Subhash Bose declared, “I shall try to win confidence of Gandhi ji. Gandhi ji is the tallest figure of india, if I fail to do so, it

¹⁷ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.46

¹⁸ Huge Toye, Subhash Chandra Bose, Jaico Publishing House, Bombay, 1959, pp.55

¹⁹ The Luminous Life of Subhash Chandra Bose, Edited Shyam Dua, pp.70

shall be my misfortune.”²⁰ However, destiny proved that he could not do so. In the Tripura session, people supported Gandhi ji’s programmes. Subhas Bose and Gandhi Ji could not reconcile and Bose resigned in April 1939 and formed ‘Forward Bloc’ on May 3, 1939. ‘Forward Bloc’ had four objectives: 1. To give leftist direction to the programmes of the congress; 2. To give last warning to the Britishers; 3. To take advantage of changing international situations; 4. To form socialist structure after Independence. Congress took a serious note of this and expelled him for three years.²¹

While touring India, he met Gandhi Ji at Wardha in June 1940 and requested for movement but later did not agree. Bose returned to Calcutta and declared that on 3rd July, 1940 Hallwell Memorial at Calcutta will be demolished. But he was arrested eleventh time a day prior to that. Though he was an elected member of the Central Legislative Assembly, yet Govt. kept him under arrest on one pretext or the other. ‘On 26th November, 1940, he wrote to Governor that “Life under existing conditions is intolerable for me. To purchase one’s continued existence by compromising with integrity and injustice is against my very grain. I would throw up my life itself, rather than pay this price.... The individual must die, so that the nation must may live. Today I must die, so that India may live and may win freedom and glory.... To my countrymen I say, ‘Forget not that the grossest crime is to compromise with injustice and wrong. Remember that eternal law: You must give life, if you want to get it. And remember that the highest virtue is to battle against inequality, no matter what the cost may be.”²² He started fast on 29th November but he was released on 5th December. However, when he reached at his ancestral house, he was put under house arrest.

The struggle of all these years convinced Subhash Bose that it will be of no use to continue fight for freedom from Indian soil. So, he decided to launch offensive from outside India. He started planning for that. He stopped taking meals and wished isolation to devote his time in worshipping, in his room, having portraits of Ramakrishna and Vivekananda. None was allowed to enter his room. Even food plate was served through a window. On the night of 16th January, 1941, he left the house at midnight 01.00AM. He reached Brori near Dhanbad at the residence of Ashok Nath, elder brother of Sharat Chandra. He was introduced as a person linked with Insurance company. Passing through north India, he reached

²⁰ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.56

²¹ Vinod Tiwari, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.60

²² V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.96-97

Peshawar and adopted name of Mohammad Ziauddin, a deaf and dumb insurance agent. He met Bhagat Ram Talwar, a member of 'Forward Bloc' and 'Kirti Kisan Dal'. After staying here for a week, they started journey for Kabul and reached there on January 31, 1941²³. It is coincidence that five days before, i.e., on 26th January, 1941 which was celebrated as Independence Day, escape of Subhash Bose was declared by the Government. Soon the rumours related to his escape started spreading ranging from different routes through which he went off to his renouncing the worldly affairs and becoming saint. Even Gandhi Ji enquired about all this from Sarat who too expressed ignorance. He stayed at Kabul for forty-six days up to 17th March, 1941. He wanted to reach Germany via Russia as both were having no attack agreement till then. After more than one month, a meeting was arranged between Italian minister Albeti Queroni and Subhash. Former sent the detailed reports dealing with Subhash's plan of revolution in India.²⁴ Ultimately, he was allowed to come to Germany via Moscow on Italian Diplomatic Passport impersonating as clerk named 'Orlando Mazetta' on a courier visa issued by Afghan Government. It took 2 months and 11 days to reach Berlin from Calcutta.

In Berlin he met Herr Von Ribbentrop and proposed three resolutions²⁵: 1. German Govt. to make arrangements for broadcasting Subhash's anti-British Propaganda from Berlin radio. 2. Govt. should allow Indian prisoners of war in Germany to be part of Indian National Army. 3. Italy, Germany and Japan the axis powers will accord recognition to Indian freedom at suitable time. Germany and Italy agreed on first two only. In the broadcasting programme Subhash was assisted by Adam Fon Traut, Director of Information and Broadcasting Department and his deputy Alexender Werth. The Azad Hind Centre was inaugurated on 2nd November, 1941 and it accepted the name of the organization was Azad Hind Centre; National Anthem – Jana Gana Mana; Emblem of the movement-Tricolour with a springing Tiger; greetings among Indians- Jai Hind, and title for Subhash Chandra Bose- Neta Ji.²⁶ During the next months he went to Rome and met his wife at Vienna also. German govt. established a special department on India under Secretary of State Wilhelm Kepler. On

²³ Dr. Sudha Singh, Mahan Krantikari, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.26.

²⁴ Capt. Gurbachan Singh Mangat, The Tiger Strikes An Unknown Chapter of Neta Ji's Life History, Gagan Publishers, Ludhiana, 1986, pp.15

²⁵ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.66-67

²⁶ N. H Pandit, Netaji, Subhash Chandra Bose, From Kabul to Battle of Imphal, Sterling Publishers Private Limited, 1988, pp.41

February 15, 1942, Singapore was conquered by Japan. On this occasion, Bose said, “I, Subhash Chandra Bose is talking to you from Azad Hind Radio. I have been waiting with silence and patience all the events for one year. Standing on the cross roads of world history,...I declare that we shall continuously fight against the British Imperialism, till India becomes the maker of his destiny itself. We shall fight to uproot British Empire from outside. I have firm belief that Indians will support us.”²⁷ Subhash wanted to meet Hitler. For this he wrote to him in April 1941 and again in May, 1941. He was able to meet Adolf Hitler on May 29, 1942. Foreign minister Herr Von Ribbentrop and Secretary of State, Keppler were also present along with interpreters.²⁸ Though nothing concrete came out of this meeting but it was settled that Bose will move to Far East and with the assistance of Japan will lead his mission of India’s freedom. Even Bose was interested in going to the East. Subhash Bose wrote in a letter to His Excellency, 22nd May, 1942, “upon my stay here for little more than a year, I think that I have done some useful and enduring work for my country. But now the time has come when the final effort should be made for achieving India’s political emancipation. For this purpose, it is absolutely essential that I should be in the East... at a place, as near to India as possible... I, therefore, confidently trust that your Excellency will be good enough to provide me with the facilities necessary for travelling to the East, so that I may perform my duty towards my country, as a leader of the national revolution....” “In another letter written on December 5, 1942, he pleaded again for his travel to the Far East.”²⁹ In November, 1942 a daughter was born to Subhash Bose. She was named Anita Bose.³⁰ So he went to Vienna to see her and came back. In January, 1943, he called his wife to Berlin while his daughter remained with her mother-in-law. ‘He left Berlin to Kiel and boarded U-190 German submarine. To keep the people in dark, recorded lectures of Bose were broadcasted regularly. Through various ships he reached Japanese port on 6th May, 1943 and reached Tokyo via aeroplane. During this journey, his name was ‘Matsuda’.’³¹

In India, Congress had launched ‘Quit India Movement’, Subhash welcomed it suggesting that Quit India Movement should be non-violent Guerilla warfare’ with aims of destroying war ammunition in India and disfunction British administration in India. In Japan,

²⁷ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.72

²⁸ N. H Pandit, Netaji, Subhash Chandra Bose, From Kabul to Battle of Imphal, pp.92

²⁹ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.121

³⁰ Ashok Kaushik, Kranti Ki Chingarian (Hindi), Satvik Sahitya Sansthan, Delhi, 2011, pp.165

³¹ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.79

Rash Behari Bose was facing many hardships and evading arrest. Ultimately at the advice of Mitsuru Toyama's, one of his followers Aizo Soma married his daughter Toshiko to him and thus he became naturalized citizen of Japan.³² He had formed an army of people of India origin and war prisoners. In 1942 June, at Bangkok conference he unfurled the 'Flag' and 'Indian League' was formed. A resolution was passed to invite Subhash to Eastern countries.³³ Rash Behari Bose also organized the Japan branch of Hindu Mahasabha. Savarkar is said to have advised him to contact the younger leader Subhash Chandra Bose.³⁴ From Singapore victory, Japan got 40,000 war prisoners who were handed over to Capt. Manmohan Singh. INA was formed.

On 10th June, 1943, Subhash met Japanese PM Tojo and sought support for India's freedom before Japanese parliament on June 16.³⁵ On 4th July, at Singapore, Rash Behari Bose handed over Indian Independence League to Subhash, who was appointed Chief Commander. Bose invited Japanese PM to take salute of 'Azad Hind Fauz' which was having women regiment named Rani Jhansi comprising of 1000 women. It was headed by Capt. Luxmi Swaminathan. On 21st October, 1943, a provisional govt. was formed. It had five ministers, eight representatives of Azad Hind Fauz and eight representatives from South East Asia. Subhash Bose was Prime Minister and chief commander. Other four ministers were Lt. Col. A. C. Chatterjee (Finance), A. M. Sahay (Secretary), M. A. Aiyar (Broadcasting), and Capt. Luxminathan (Women Organization).³⁶ On 23rd October Japan recognized this govt. followed by Germany, Italy, Croatia, Manchuko, Nanking, Phillipines, Thailand and Burma. On 24th October, Azad Hind Fauz declared war against Britain and America.³⁷

To chart out war plans, talks were held between Subhash and Japan's Chief Commander Field Marshall Count Terauchi. Japan wanted that 'Azad Hind Fauz' to support Japanese army but Bose wished independent operations. Ultimately it was decided that one regiment of 'Azad Hind Fauz' will participate with Japanese army and after its success 'Azad Hind Fauz' will operate independently in the war.³⁸ 'Azad Hind Fauz' was having four

³² N. H Pandit, Netaji, Subhash Chandra Bose, From Kabul to Battle of Imphal, pp.100

³³ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.77

³⁴ N. H Pandit, Netaji, Subhash Chandra Bose, From Kabul to Battle of Imphal, pp.101

³⁵ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.81

³⁶ Shantanu Dey, Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose- A Glance through the great man's epic journey (eBook), pothi.com, pp.166

³⁷ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.146

³⁸ N. H Pandit, Netaji, Subhash Chandra Bose, From Kabul to Battle of Imphal, pp.241

Brigades: Gandhi Brigade, Nehru Brigade, Azad Brigade and Subhash Brigade (formed with selected soldiers from the other three brigades). Last was headed by Shah Nawaj Khan. In February, 1944 This brigade along with Japanese army captured some areas and reached Mowdak. As it was difficult to send ammunition to Mowdak, Japanese army decided to leave it but Subhash brigade refused. Two battalions of Azad Hind Fauz reached Kohima and captured it. Gandhi brigade attacked Imphal and fought against the Britishers in June 1944.³⁹ According to Major General Woodburn Kirby, “If Imphal had fallen to the Japanese one of the consequences could have been a revolt in Bengal and Bihar against British rule in India which might well have been on a far larger scale than riots of 1942.”⁴⁰ But it was an irony of Netaji’s fate that Imphal did not fall, mainly due to failure of strategic plans and nature’s fury in the form of torrential rains in the war area.

However, at this crucial juncture, Japanese army was called back due to American army’s presence in Pacific Ocean. On one side Japanese help stopped and on the other side weather was not inclined. In spite of all the difficulties they continued their march, uttering, “whatever it is we shall not stop. We shall rest only after reaching Delhi. Mother land had called us. Now victory and victory is our slogan.”⁴¹ On 31st December, 1944 British army landed in Burma. When he was informed by Gen. Isoda that some soldiers surrendered in the battle of Irawaddy river, he issued a proclamation that “anyone who attempted to retreat shot to death.”⁴²

He was taking keen interest at micro level in war operations even at the risk of his life. One day Bose himself came to inspect the Brigade led by Shah Nawaj, the later objected, “Neta Ji you are going selfish. You are endangering your life to show personal bravery. You have no right to put your life in danger like this. Your life is not yours. It is priceless heritage of India and in our safe concerns, I shall not put in any danger.”⁴³ Bose replied, “Shah Nawaj do not worry about my safety. As I knew that England has not yet produced the bomb that can kill Subhash Bose.”⁴⁴

³⁹ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.84

⁴⁰ N. H Pandit, Netaji, Subhash Chandra Bose, From Kabul to Battle of Imphal, pp.267

⁴¹ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.85

⁴² V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.157

⁴³ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp. 86

⁴⁴ Shah Nawaj Khan, My Memories of I. N. A. and its Netaji, Rajkamal publications, Delhi, 1946, pp.179

In April 1945, Bose was asked to leave Rangoon where his last birthday was celebrated by weighing him in gold, collected from among Indians, twice his weight.....Habib Sahib of Rangoon donated all his landed property, cash and jewellery valued at Rupees one crore and thirty lakhs and asked Neta Ji for a pair of Khaki shirts and shorts, to work for the movement.”⁴⁵ In May, 1945 Germany surrendered and Hitler committed suicide. On 6th and 9th August, USA threw atom bombs at Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan and compelled Japan to surrender. Even at this stage, he was expecting that USA and Britain will fight against USSR, so he wanted to go to Russia. He gave a message to John Thivi of Indian Independence League that I am writing to you just before going to long journey via air route and who knows, some incident engulfs me”⁴⁶

Subhash Bose in his last order said, “Comrades...we have been overwhelmed by an undreamt-of crisis. You may perhaps feel that you have failed in your mission to liberate india. But let me tell you that this failure is only of a temporary nature. No setback and no defeat can undo your positive achievements of the past... he continued, “The roads to Delhi are many, and Delhi still remains our goal. The sacrifices of your immortal comrades and of yourselves will certainly achieve their fulfilment. There is no power on earth that can keep India enslaved. India shall be free before long.”⁴⁷

Netaji left Singapore by a plane on August 15, 1945 to Saigon. Field Marshal Terachi arranged his flight secretly at personal level. On 17th August, 1945, plane took off from Saigon. Subhash Bose was accompanied by Habib-ur-Rehman and they reached Touraine and then Taipeh on 18th August the fateful day. But as soon as the plane took off from Taipeh in the afternoon, it crashed. On 23rd August, 1945 Tokyo News Agency gave the news that Subhash Bose got badly injured in plane crash on August 18, 1945 and expired on the same night. Col. Habib-ur-Rehman (who was accompanying him in plane crash), Major General Shah Nawaj and Col. Sehgal have verified this fact. ⁴⁸

Conclusions: Subhash Chandra Bose stands as unique patriot in the history of India’s struggle for freedom. His distinctive approach towards freedom movement is highly debated even today. His tireless efforts with nationalistic zeal to free India, firstly within India and

⁴⁵ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.158.

⁴⁶ Ashok Kaushik, Kranti Ki Chingarian (Hindi), pp.167

⁴⁷ V. S. Patil, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose His Contribution to Indian Nationalism, pp.160

⁴⁸ C. L. Sharma, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, pp.89

later on from foreign soil make every Indian feel proud of him. He was not merely a dauntless patriot but also a perceptive and progressive thinker with rare insight into India's socio-economic and political issues. Inspired with philosophy of Ramakrishna-Vivekananda, he was more realistic than his contemporaries. His supreme sacrifice along with his sensitizing words "Give me blood, I shall give you freedom" will continue to inspire and guide millions of patriotic Indians.